

METHODOLOGY OF DEMOCRATIZATION OF THE POLITICAL SYSTEM

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Abstract. *In this article, the author revealed the structural and institutional factors of democratic governance through a comparative analysis of the fundamentals of democratization system of the public administration.*

Keywords: *democratic transit, legitimacy, social system, state power, reform, public organizations, public control.*

Introduction

The movement toward a democratic state in different countries occurs under different conditions and in different forms, which is a proven fact. An etymological and semantic analysis of democracy shows that it is applied to various social spheres and activities such as “political democracy,” “economic democracy,” “democratic values,” “democratic state,” “democratic society,” “democratic governance,” “democratic development.”

This does not imply that the democratic features of modernizing a particular country are meant to create political systems similar to those in developed Western countries. Indeed, in every country, democracy has its own form. Because the establishment of democratic values in people’s consciousness occurs in a unique way, taking into account the nature of thinking that has been formed over hundreds of years. The decisive factor for the success of this process is, of course, that reforms are based on a long-term conceptual strategy.

The priority tasks outlined in the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev “On Approving the Concept of Administrative Reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated September 8, 2017, No. PF-5185 are aimed at implementing the vital idea: “The people should be served by state institutions, not the state institutions by the people” [1], and at the same time, initiated a new stage of democratic development in our country.

Today, world practice shows that there are internal mechanisms ensuring the rapid development of a democratic society. In the current stage of renewal and modernization processes in our country, reforms aimed at creating a strong foundation for civil society are being developed on a wide scale, while particular attention is paid to developing the institutional and socio-economic foundations of democracy at the societal level using the latest conceptual approaches. Implementing these tasks, in turn, serves as the basis for expanding human rights and freedoms, that is, for carrying out fundamental reforms aimed at strengthening the social core of democratic renewal and liberalization processes.

At present, in reforming the management system of the state, which is the most important subject of the democratic political system, the introduction of new tasks is primarily based on the diversity of political institutions and non-governmental organizations, as well as strengthening their role, and increasing the political activity of the population, which forms the basis for the evolutionary democratization of societal life.

Almost all modern scientific schools and centers studying public administration emphasize that governance can only function within a democratic society. For example, supporters of “strong administration” (M. Weber, A. Gaudner, etc.) believed that only a democratic form of government could ensure efficient bureaucratic mechanisms. Representatives of the “leadership approach” (A. Osborne and A. Gaebler) argue that state governance should not be vertical but rather horizontal. In this way, taking into account the influence of civil society institutions in horizontal governance when making political decisions is considered a sign of the existence of a democratic society [2; p.31].

In our opinion, the implementation of democracy in the field of horizontal governance helps the faster development of civil society institutions in society. In this, the most important general condition for the success of democratization is political stability, which envisages the reform of society within the law while preserving the ability of state institutions to govern the country.

From the 1980s, a new research direction initially regionally, and later globally, was formed in social sciences under the name “modern transitology.” If we approach this concept from an etymological perspective, modern transitology involves the analysis of socio-political changes during the transition period related to the formation of a new qualitative state of the social relations system. However, in practice, the term “transitology” has a narrow meaning, and research in this area studied the process of transitioning state power from autocratic forms to democracy. Within the social sciences, as a relatively independent discipline, transitology is the study of democratization [3; p.150]. In general terms, democratization is the process of political, economic, and socio-cultural changes aimed at establishing a democratic system.

According to Russian scholar A. Melville, “The history of the formation of democratic norms is connected with the process of developing, expanding, and renewing democratic ideas and principles, institutions, and order.” He believes that “democracy is a constantly moving process of democratization” [4; p.48].

A natural question arises: how does the transition to democratic governance occur? Experts today do not have a clear answer to this question. This is not because research has not reached a consensus, but because strategies for democratizing governance in different countries are connected with different reform processes.

For example, Doctor of Philosophy Sh.O. Mamadaliyev, in his studies, seeks the Eastern characteristics of democracy in the institution of popular rule. To do this, he refers to social-religious concepts deeply rooted in the consciousness, lifestyle, and mentality of Eastern peoples: Hindu-Buddhism, Confucianism, Zoroastrianism, and Islam.

According to the scholar, in the East, democracy has an elitist and statist character, that is, the just king is an institution that ensures the welfare of the people and moral-cultural development. Therefore, Eastern thinkers, relying on the Eastern lifestyle and mentality, advanced various ideas and concepts about a just king, a benevolent ruler, and a society of goodness. If theocratic approaches prevailed in these views, by the 19th century, approaches to state governance began to include secular knowledge and modern methods, referring to world, especially European, experiences [5; p.47].

In our opinion, depending on the democratization strategy chosen by the authorities and political institutions of a particular state, different paths of democratic transition can be distinguished. Also, democratization processes can be defined based on specific research subjects and objects. Undoubtedly, for example, the process of democratizing governance in Germany or

Poland differs from the democratization process in Uzbekistan or Kazakhstan. Naturally, democratization processes may be peaceful or violent, revolutionary or evolutionary, adopted from outside or formed under internal change influences.

Moreover, any state implementing democratic reforms must pay attention to a number of important and urgent tasks: strengthening the democratic political system, developing the constitutional foundations of state and society, establishing civil society, defining democratic functions of state power, transitioning to a market economy, as well as forming stable foreign policy directions during the transition period that fully meet the interests of the country.

One of the important aspects of analyzing conceptual approaches is examining the “democracy transit” model. In the 1960s, within the concept of modernization, American political scientists G. Almond and S. Verba developed the theory of political culture. According to them, the political culture and activity of citizens are key indicators and measures of a democratic state. Almond and Verba applied components such as “cognitive orientation,” “affective orientation,” and “approach from the evaluation perspective.” Unlike economic theory, the process of democratizing the state and society is not about economic development but about political norms, relationships, and behaviors. The founders of this theory primarily developed concepts of civil culture that are inclined toward the formation and effective functioning of democratic institutions. Civil culture was characterized by a high level of mutual trust, compromise on mutual interests and relations, and principles of tolerance [6; p.58].

That democracy is a reality connected with state governance is recognized, in one way or another, by many researchers. Democracy is related to the political system, which ensures an individual’s political freedom and democratic rights, as well as the conformity of formal constitutional and legal norms with political reality. At the same time, the political system not only expresses broad and diverse political processes, but also, on the one hand, represents the interests of the state, political system, and political groups, and on the other hand, organizes socio-political reality, public movements, and the activities of civil institutions from the perspective of overall democratic development.

Thus, democratization processes do not emerge spontaneously, nor are they the movement of groups claiming to represent the will of the majority; rather, they are the result of conscious activities that follow the laws of social development and integrate these laws into practice. Historical-social development shows that the main subject of this activity is primarily the state and its political order.

However, not all political systems or states rely on democracy and collective governance, but they contain elements and forces aspiring toward social development. When these elements and forces support conceptual models of social development, real opportunities for democratic development arise.

Currently, two approaches are distinguished in studying state governance democratization processes: structural and organizational.

The first approach pays particular attention to structural factors that shape the socio-economic and cultural values of the state and the nation, as well as democratic principles, in the process of democratization. Proponents of the structural approach, such as S. Lipset, G. Almond, S. Verba, and D. Rostow, reveal the structural foundations of democratic regimes by identifying the primary interconnections between them as factors of socio-economic and cultural change. This approach explains democratic processes not from the perspective of participants’ subjective goals,

but from the standpoint of objective structures. Furthermore, representatives of this approach highlight three primary systemic types of democratization:

1. Achieving national unity;
2. Attaining a high level of socio-economic development;
3. Recognition of democratic principles, trust in democratic institutions and citizenship, and acknowledgment of national cultural norms and values.

In contrast, proponents of the organizational approach (G. O'Donnell, F. Schmitter, A. Przeworski) emphasize that democratization processes depend on the mutual agreement among competitive political elites, the conscious choice to reach consensus, the organizational forms and institutions of a new social structure, and the principle that every citizen in a democratic political system has the right to participate in governance (the principle of universal participation). They also stress political equality, where all votes have the same value (the principle of political equality), and that decisions should be made according to the will of the majority (the majority rule principle) [7; p.128].

Additionally, Russian political scientist L.V. Smorgunov enriches the scientific approaches to democracy by proposing two theoretical paradigms: liberal democratization and radical democratization [8; p.59]. According to him, these elements of democratization help define the boundaries of the "state-society-citizen" concept. In the process of liberal democratization, citizens may exhibit arbitrariness and disregard for the law, whereas radical democratization prioritizes social equality and the general public's political participation over the freedom of a single individual.

The criteria for democratizing society have evolved in form and content throughout historical development and continue to do so today. Indeed, even in the most developed countries, the process of democratization has not reached its highest, ideal stage. Each nation and society, in each historical period, has its own specific interpretation and application of democracy. This specificity is shaped by factors such as the historical path traversed by the people, national mentality, traditions, and the character of existing social relations. Nonetheless, general criteria for determining the nature of democratization exist, which relate to adherence to democratic principles, the presence and functioning of democratic institutions. Fundamentally, democratization is a factor enabling the holistic development of the individual and ensuring harmony between personal and societal interests.

The development of a democratic environment and its foundations is a unique phenomenon for Uzbekistan, where the presidential model has proven to be the most suitable form for implementing both democracy and strong governance. Russian political science candidate Svetlana Gordiyenko emphasizes that the process of transition to democracy requires, from a strategic and tactical perspective, strong presidential governance. The President should not only implement modernization but also guarantee democratic rights and freedoms and neutralize destabilizing influences in society [9; p.4].

In this context, the institution of the Presidency in Uzbekistan has emerged through the integration of national traditions and values with the experience of developed democratic states. Presidential power is embedded in the legal system as part of the principle of separation of powers, a hallmark of the rule of law. Establishing the office of the President in Uzbekistan created mechanisms for harmonizing the functions of the legislative, executive, and judicial branches, with a primary focus on coordinating the activities of the legislative and executive authorities.

It is important to note that in states where the presidential form of governance operates, the President serves as the head of state and executive power, holding extensive authority and occupying a central position within the system of state organs. In this form, the principle of separation of powers is realized functionally, institutionally, and personally in practice. The distinctive features of the presidential form of governance include: the President being both head of state and government, eliminating the need for a separate Prime Minister; the presence of a Vice President; direct, universal presidential elections, granting the President authority derived directly from the people; the President forming the government independently of parliament, with the government accountable solely to the President; and the President not having the authority to dissolve parliament.

Globally, hybrid governance systems are classified based on whether the presidential or parliamentary role predominates, resulting in presidential-parliamentary or parliamentary-presidential forms. In our view, the powers of the President, as defined by the Constitution and laws, and his practical role indicate that Uzbekistan has adopted a presidential-parliamentary hybrid governance system.

Analyzing the interplay between democracy and power, it is clear that democracy cannot survive without strong authority; however, the mere presence of strong state institutions does not guarantee democracy. In a transformational context, they may exert pressure on democratic systems or even undermine them. Conversely, weak state institutions objectively reduce the effectiveness of a functioning democratic system.

The degree of alignment between governance structures and society is manifested through transparency, the development of independent mass media, and the population's right to access information. Democratization proceeds alongside societal pluralism, the growth of political parties and movements, ideologies, diverse worldviews, and political opinions. The development of new principles in state governance largely depends on these processes, which provide the basis for forming and consolidating new qualities in governance. In advanced democracies, strong authority, grounded in the rule of law and justice, relies directly on public opinion in its activities.

In conclusion, the most important element of establishing effective administrative-state governance is the process of democratization and its consolidation. The “Uzbekistan – 2030” strategy, approved by Presidential Decree PF-158 of September 11, 2023, represents a national democratic strategy aimed at deepening democratic reforms in state and society amid global transformations, with defined objectives in judicial, legal, economic, social, and security spheres.

Conceptual analysis of democratization during state reforms shows that these processes are interrelated, and their precise boundaries are often indistinguishable. From examining the role of state governance in democratization, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. A universal conceptual model that can define the conditions for democratization cannot be established due to the diverse conditions in each society;
2. Democratization is influenced by a complex set of factors;
3. Democratic processes require a systemic approach, as elite willingness alone is insufficient without societal demand;
4. The analysis of democratization must synthesize structural and organizational models, as no single model can fully encompass the process;
5. Consolidating democracy is crucial, as democratization will not yield desired results without societal integration;

6. Democratization is directly linked to state governance, which is the primary mechanism capable of fulfilling the requirements of democratic transition.

Effective state governance is therefore a fundamental element in the process of democratizing society, reflecting the intrinsic connection between state and society. Consequently, the key democratic principles of current governance in Uzbekistan include:

- ensuring social equality;
- gradual decentralization of state governance;
- implementing effective, bureaucracy-free governance while preventing corruption;
- increasing transparency and efficiency in decision-making processes;
- creating mechanisms that ensure citizens' rights and freedoms;
- realizing the principle that "state institutions serve the people, not vice versa."

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